

RESIDUAL STRENGTH OF GRAPHITE/BMI COMPOSITES AFTER LONG TERM CYCLICAL COMPRESSION

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ABSTRACT

The prediction of residual strength after compression cycling was studied for graphite/bismaleimide plates. A method for compression cycling of large numbers of samples at various loads and temperatures was devised. Changes in ply properties were used to predict laminate strengths using a general laminate theory together with the Tsai-Wu failure criterion. The failure prediction explored the choice of ply degradation and the use of the interaction parameter, F_{xy} . A modified uniaxial compression test was used to measure F_{xy} . The feasibility of following changes in the interaction parameter are discussed.

Keywords: Strength prediction, compression cycling, interaction parameter

1. INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics are candidates for future commercial aircraft because of their high strength to weight ratios and consequent fuel savings. Supersonic wing and fuselage sections may be subject to cyclical compression stresses with simultaneous exposure to moderate temperatures. Graphite/bismaleimide was studied because of promising tensile fatigue resistance and also because of lack of data on long term (strength) durability. Related work [1] recently reported on prediction of creep strains of non-linear viscoelastic composites with simultaneous aging and internal damage.

2. THEORY

2.1 General Approach

The well-known Tsai-Wu strength criterion [2] was chosen as a means of using test data to make long term strength predictions. Its basic form;

$$F_{ij}\sigma_i\sigma_j + F_i\sigma_i = 1 \quad (i,j = 1,2,3,4,5,6) \quad (1)$$

may be simplified for a thin, specially orthotropic ply under plane stress relative to the symmetry axes x-y as:

$$F_{xx} \sigma_x^2 + 2F_{xy} \sigma_x \sigma_y + F_{yy} \sigma_y^2 + F_x \sigma_x + F_y \sigma_y + F_{ss} \sigma_s^2 = 1 \quad (2)$$

where $F_{xx} = 1/XX'$, $F_{yy} = 1/YY'$, $F_{ss} = 1/S^2$, $F_x = (1/X)-(1/X')$, $F_y = (1/Y)-(1/Y')$

$$\text{and } F_{xy} = F_{xy}^* [F_{xx} F_{yy}]^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

X, X' = longitudinal tensile and compressive; Y, Y' = transverse tensile and compressive and S = the shear, strengths. The interaction parameter F_{12} is determined from combined loading tests, and is related to the normalized F_{xy}^* in Equation 3.

Figure 1 — Failure Surfaces in Stress Space for Various Values of F_{xy}^*

The "Genlam" program [2] uses Equation 2 to predict the first ply failure of a laminate based on the history dependence of the ply parameters and hence strength tensors F_{ij} and F_i . This through-the-thickness point stress laminate program outputs the usual stiffness constants and ply stresses and strains. The model predicts the first ply failure stress and then assumes the failed ply contributes only a fraction (degradation factor D.F) of its properties to the laminate until ultimate failure. In addition, it uses the quadratic failure criterion to compute the strength ratios (R = ratio of strength to applied stress) of both intact and degraded matrix laminates. The strength prediction for a laminate (when $R(\text{ultimate}) = 1$) assumes the ply values values $E_s(t,s,T)$, $X(t,s,T)$, $X'(t,s,T)$ etc. are known.

2.2 The Interaction Parameter

Can long term changes in the interaction parameter F_{xy} due to damage, aging, etc., be measured and/or predicted? Both rotations and translations of the elliptical failure surfaces may occur in biaxial stress space [3]. Figure 1 shows failure surfaces for various values of F_{xy}^* . To ensure a closed failure surface, the stability limits are

$$-[F_{xx} F_{yy}]^{1/2} < F_{xy} < [F_{xx} F_{yy}]^{1/2} \quad (4)$$

which from Equation 3 means $-1 < F_{xy}^* < 1$. Measurement of the interaction parameter requires a biaxial stress state, such as an off-axis strength test [4,5], testing of cylinders [6], or (proposed) prevention of perpendicular displacements on a uniaxial strain test [7]. Estimations of F_{xy} have been based on the modified Hill method [8], the generalized von Mises method

[9], geometric [10] and stability [11] considerations. Numerical experiments comparing $F_{xy}^* = \pm 0.5$ with $F_{xy}^* = 0$ concluded that for certain conditions the maximum error is less than 10% [8]; for general conditions, they can be as high as 40% [12].

3. EXPERIMENTAL

3.1 Static and Cyclical Compression Testing

Samples (8 or 16 plies each 0.1473 mm thick) were fabricated by the Boeing Aircraft Company from the IM7/5260-H graphite/bismaleimide system. A quasi-isotropic laminate $([+45/0/-45/90]_{2s})$ was chosen to test predictions based on ply (0, 90 or ± 45) data. A test matrix used two time periods (zero and three months), two temperatures (ambient and 300°F), two compressive stress levels (one zero), with both static (S) and cyclic (C - 4h on, 1h off) stresses/temperatures.

Figure 2 — Schematic Diagram of Compression Test Fixture

Compressive stresses require prevention of sample buckling which raises questions on the uniformity of the stress throughout each sample. The method chosen was based on the compression between links of a chain loaded in tension [1]. Figure 2 shows schematically the fixture, sample, shims, and tension links. Samples were strain gaged for long term creep measurements, requiring holes in the steel restraining plates. Electrical heating and compressed air flow cooling gave thermal time constants of 35 minutes. The environment was air at 50% R.H. (We are presently examining 95% R.H. and the effect of hydraulic fluids). Table 1 summarizes the matrix of test conditions. (See Table 5 for stress levels.)

3.2 Measurement of Ply Properties

Mechanical properties (E_x , E_y , E_s , X , X' , Y , Y' and S) were obtained by standard tensile/compression test methods after the L1-L11 exposures. An Instron 4500/4505 controlled by a Labview II program on a Macintosh SE which recorded the applied load and crosshead displacement. The strains were sensed by Micromeritics (Vishay) type AE strain gages (although WK gages were used to monitor strains during long term exposure at 149°C). Model P3500 strain indicators supplied a voltage signal recorded by a Soltec 2000 Chart Recorder. Compression testing was done with a test fixture manufactured by Wyoming Test Fixtures specifically for the Boeing Modified ASTM D 695 test method. Poisson's ratios were measured in accordance with ASTM standard E 132 and gave $\nu_{xy} = 0.279$ and $\nu_{yx} = 0.028$. Table 2 summarizes preliminary data, mostly averages of two measurements.

Table 1 – Comparison of Measured and Predicted UTS for Quasi A Layouts

Test Case	Time (h)	T°C	Load	UTS Measured		UTS Predicted D.F. = 0.3		UTS Predicted D.F. = 0.2	
				MPa(ksi)		MPa (ksi)		MPa (ksi)	
L1	zero	25	zero	921	(133.6)	789	(114.4)	766	(111)
L2	zero	25	S	894	(129.6)	773	(112.1)	795	(115.3)
L3	2260	25	zero	801	(116.13)	706	(102.4)	877	(127.1)
L4	2260	25	S	909	(131.85)	810	(117.5)	892	(129.3)
L5	2260	25	C	847	(122.88)	795	(115.3)	817	(118.5)
L6	zero	149	zero	808	(117.2)	799	(115.8)	817	(118.5)
L7	zero	149	S	815	(118.2)	725	(105.1)	743	(107.8)
L8	2260	149	zero	851	(123.43)	691	(100.2)	840	(121.8)
L9	2260	149C	zero	812	(117.720)	632	(91.6)	772	(112.0)
L10	2260	149	S	853	(123.69)	766	(111)	825	(119.6)
L11	2260	149C	C	768	(111.4)	699	(101.3)	795	(115.3)

L1 = as-received (fabricated) plus about 6 months storage; L2 = 4h load at 25°C only; L6 = heat 149°C for 4 h, no load, cool; L7 = heat 149°C for 4h with load

Table 2 – Ply Properties Measured on 0, 90 and ±45 Laminates

Test	X MPa	X' MPa	Y MPa	Y' MPa	S MPa	E _x GPa	E' _x GPa	E _y GPa	E' _y GPa	E _s GPa
L1	2324	1615	71.0	311	168	152	51.2	8.69	8.38	7.52
L2	2341	1497	62.8	286	163	160	40.3	8.62	6.00	11.45
L3	2502	1583	61.0	292	108	157	39.1	9.24	8.34	7.59
L4	2596	1823	60.7	294	110	205	48.3	9.72	4.14	2.62
L5	2394	1782	57.2	313	180	240	24.4	9.66	8.48	3.86
L6	2374	1512	67.6	274	115	221	18.8	8.69	8.28	8.48
L7	2147	1777	75.2	293	163	149	20.7	8.76	7.59	3.31
L8	2500	1625	64.1	236	171	159	48.5	10.28		5.10
L9	2308	1537	53.4	(207)	173	156	36.1	8.97		3.41
L10	2417	1713	54.3	(138)	172	202	30.3	9.24	3.59	2.41
L11	(2276)	1909	(52)	106	176	(159)		(8.97)		2.00

() estimated value

3.3 Measurement of the Interaction Parameter

Figure 1 shows that the strength curves of various values of F_{12} in the third and fourth quadrant are well separated and thus any changes in F_{xy} should be most readily detectable in a biaxial compressive state. The biaxial load state was applied by a novel modification of the Boeing modified test method BSS 7260 of ASTM D695 compression test using available 0-deg and 90-deg (Type III) tabbed unidirectional test coupons [12]. A compressive load was applied in the transverse direction by means of a bench vice and a clamp in the direction perpendicular to the sample edge. This allows an axial applied compressive stress to generate an even greater transverse compressive stress. Teflon lined steel shims enhanced uniform load distribution. A 0/90 rosette strain gage was bonded on both sides to determine compressive moduli and Poisson's ratios. The failure stresses, baseline ply properties from Table 1 and equations 1-4 were used to determine F_{xy} .

4. RESULTS

Table 2 indicates no significant reduction with time for X , S , E_x , or E_y . The fiber direction compressive strength X' deteriorated slightly during unloaded thermal cycling (L7-L9). Y and Y' showed slight reductions at all high temperature exposures as long as stress was also applied. E'_x reduced during room temperature stress cycling (L5). E'_y deteriorated during static loading conditions, both at room and elevated temperature (L4,L10). The shear modulus E_s was reduced by all long term exposure; somewhat more with stress than with elevated temperature. The ultimate tensile strengths measured for the quasi-isotropic laminate given in Table 1 are plotted in Figure 3, together with the prediction using "Genlam," the quadratic failure criteria and the ply properties of Table 2. The degradation factor (0.2 or 0.3) and $F_{xy}^* = -0.5$ were held constant. The L1 ply properties and biaxial failure stresses σ_1 and σ_2 were combined to calculate F_{xy} and F_{xy}^* . The results for two 90-deg and six 0-deg samples are given in Table 3.

Figure 3 — Measured and Predicted Ultimate Tensile Strengths for a Quasi-Isotropic Laminate

Table 3 — Summary of F_{xy} Measurements

Sample Layup	σ_1 MPa	σ_2 MPa	F_{xy} MPa ⁻²	F_{xy}^* MPa ⁻²
[90] ₈	-121.2±9	-367±14	-1.16e-5	-3.66±0.7
[0] ₈	-1180±99	-31.9±7	+1.22e-5	3.84±0.9

The stability limits from Equation 4 are $-3.17e-6 < F_{xy} < 3.17e-6$ and $-1 < F_{xy}^* < 1$. Two additional methods of analyzing the data were developed. The constants of the Tsai-Wu failure criterion (F_{xx} , F_{yy} , etc.) from Equation 2 were combined with five biaxial data points from the five data sets whose values of F_{xy} were closest to the stability limit. This gave five equations

with five unknown strength parameters. Another method was based on a least mean squares solution in the form of an ellipse. Since the error could be either in the σ_1 or σ_2 direction, Equation 2 was expressed in terms of $\sigma_1 = r\cos\theta$ and $s_2 = r\sin\theta$ where $\theta = \tan^{-1}(\sigma_2/\sigma_1)$. This assumes the error is in the radial direction from a data point. The least squares ellipse yields a value for all the strength parameters. The results are compared with approximations in Table 4. A series of numerical experiments with variation of only one property at a time were carried out. There exists an optimum biaxial stress ratio for determining F_{12} and it was shown [6] that adjustment of the ratio σ_1/σ_2 could be made to obtain F_{xy} within the stability limits.

Table 4 – Summary of Interaction Determinations

Present Tests	Mean F_{xy} (MPa) ⁻²	F_{xy}^*
Modified Strain Test $\sigma_2 > \sigma_1$	-1.17e-5	-3.86233Y
Modified Strain Test $\sigma_1 > \sigma_2$	1.22e-5	
Least Mean Square	5.27e-6	1.66
Elliptical Solution of 5 [0] ₈ pts.	0.47e-6	0.148
Tsai-Hahn [9] (approximation)	-1.59e-6	-0.5
Wu-Stachurski [10] (")	-0.22e-6	-0.07
Wilczynski [11] (")	-1.3e-6	-0.41

5. ANALYSIS

Analysis of Figure 3 showed that the trends in predicted ultimate strength for the laminate followed well the predictions based on the trends in the ply properties. However, the actual level of the UTS was low in a number of cases. Parametric analysis showed that changing ν_{12} from 0.279 to 0.2 or increasing F_{xy}^* to -0.4 had negligible effect. The laminate strength correlates with the ply strength X, but is not sensitive to changes in the shear strength S. A degradation factor of 0.2 gave better agreement with measured results than one of 0.3. The long term loading stresses for 0, 90, ± 45 test laminates are compared to the ply stresses during the long term axial loading of the quasi-isotropic laminate in Table 5. Thus long term degradation predictions of the quasi laminate may be related to the stress induced degradation of the individual plies.

Table 5 – Summary of Stresses in Laminates During Long Term Testing

Ply Layup	Applied Axial Stress σ_1 (MPa)	Percent of UCS at 25°C	Ply Stresses (MPa)		
			σ_x	σ_y	σ_s
[0] ₁₆	-362 (-52.4ksi)	19%	-361	0	0
[90] ₁₆	-94.5 (-13.7ksi)	30%	0	-94.5	0
[± 45] _{4s}	-186 (-27 ksi)	55%	-192	5.8	± 93
[45/0/-45/90] _{2s}	-186 (-27ksi)	22%			
0-deg			-542	21.3	-8.9
90-deg			148	-2.6	0
45-deg			-197	9.4	8.9

It is seen that in the quasi-isotropic laminate, ply stresses are similar to those used for the data base except for the 90° plies which see a large tensile stress. The predictions are therefore based on plies with mainly compressive loading induced degradation. This suggests that long term transverse tensile loading data be also obtained.

The strength predictions for the quasi-isotropic laminate were only slightly sensitive to the chosen value of F_{xy}^* . Use of Wilczynski's approximation [11];

$$F_{xy}^* = -(XY + X'Y')^{-1} [1/(XX'YY')]^{-1/2} \quad (5)$$

indicated $-0.48 < F_{xy}^* < -0.40$ in all cases, and the use of -0.4 rather than -0.5 did not alter the relative results.

6. DISCUSSION

Refinements of the prediction theory requires time varying changes in the stress state of each ply due to creep processes and loading cycle parameters, as recovery occurs between loading. The "Genlam" program does not consider that compressive moduli differ from tensile, as Table 2 shows. An iterative approach for plies in compression is suggested.

The measurements of F_{xy} do not readily agree with predictions and indeed it has been difficult to keep them within the required stability limits. We note that F_{xy} is the culmination of a series of experiments. Errors in determination of $X, X', Y, Y', E_x, E_y, \nu_{xy}$ and ν_{yx} will adversely effect the ability to determine F_{xy} , regardless of the accuracy of the strain measurement at failure. The third quadrant holds the variability of compressive failures, which can occur by a variety of modes such as microbuckling, matrix yielding and/or shear. Misalignment easily induces shear stresses, assumed equal to zero in the above analysis. Problems include the constancy of the Poisson's ratios and compressive moduli to failure. (E_x' may show considerable reduction at large compressive loads). Errors in the use of approximations can also be shown to vary with the biaxial load ratio.

7. CONCLUSIONS

A method of compression stress cycling was developed for long term evaluation of the residual stress of composite materials. Early data with graphite/bismaleimide shows some deterioration with combined stress cycling to about 25% of the ultimate compressive strength and temperature cycling between room temperature and 149°C. Application of the Tsai-Wu quadratic failure criterion gave good agreement with measured ultimate tensile strengths when a degradation factor of 0.2 was employed. Degradation data for all ply properties are needed at the same stress levels as they experience in the test laminate (or until complete $X(t,s,T), X'(t,s,T)$, etc. data become available).

A modified biaxial load method with thin plates was devised to measure the interaction parameter F_{xy} in order to follow possible changes in it due to various stress/temperature cycling conditions. Rosette strain gages are recommended to detect any shear stresses. A major problem with experimentally determining F_{xy} is the large number of samples required. At this time, we do not feel that attempts to monitor changes in F_{xy} are justified unless failure mechanisms can be shown to remain constant and optimum biaxial stress ratios can be utilized. Instead, the success in predicting failure strengths justifies using a constant assumed F_{xy} , at least until much longer term strength data prove otherwise.

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